

Status report of air quality in Europe for year 2024, using validated data

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1 Summary

The *2024 Status report of air quality in Europe* presents summarized information on the status of air quality in Europe for the protection of health. It is based on 2024 validated monitoring data⁽¹⁾ officially reported under the Ambient Air Quality Directives in the 2025 September reporting cycle⁽²⁾. It provides information on the following pollutants, regulated by the Ambient Air Quality Directives (AAQD) (EU, 2004, 2008, 2024)

- PM₁₀: Particulate matter with a diameter of 10 µm or less
- PM_{2.5}: Particulate matter with a diameter of 2.5 µm or less
- O₃: Tropospheric ozone
- NO₂: Nitrogen dioxide
- BaP: Benzo[a]pyrene
- SO₂: Sulphur dioxide
- CO: Carbon monoxide
- C₆H₆: Benzene
- As: Arsenic
- Cd: Cadmium
- Pb: Lead
- Ni: Nickel

It also offers a comparison with the situation in previous years.

Data included in this report was received by 09 February 2026 from the reporting countries. By that date the reporting status of 2024 validated data is summarized in Figure 1, where a green box indicates that the referred pollutant was reported by the referred country and a grey box indicates the contrary (that the referred pollutant was not reported by the referred country). Please see editorial notes at the end of this Chapter on additional information on the data used. The number of stations by country reporting each pollutant, with the minimum data coverage for at least one of the aggregations used in the report, is also included in Figure 1, while Table

¹Please be aware that some countries also report official data from modelling applications. Those data are available at <https://discomap.eea.europa.eu/AirQualityModellingViewer/>

²<https://eedmz1-cws-wp-air02-dev.azurewebsites.net/aq-ereporting/>

3 in the Annex summarizes the number of stations, with the minimum data coverage for at least one of the aggregations used in the report, at different country aggregations. Data from stations that do not fulfil the criteria from Box 1.1 are excluded from this report. Please be aware that the number of stations presented in Figure 1 and Table 3, that corresponds to all reported stations fulfilling the minimum data coverage criteria for at least one of the aggregations used in the report, may be different to the one presented in the corresponding boxplots, as there could be some stations not fulfilling the minimum data coverage criteria for the corresponding aggregation.

Figure 1: Number of stations, for each country and each pollutant, that in 2024 reported data with the minimum data coverage for at least one of the aggregations used in the report, by 09 February 2026

	PM10	PM2.5	O3	NO2	BaP	SO2	CO	C6H6	As	Cd	Pb	Ni
Albania								5				
Andorra	1	1	2	1		1	1					
Austria	125	67	107	143	32	59	26	22	12	13	12	11
Belgium	81	81	35	132	11	21	18	34	27	27	29	27
Bosnia and Herzegovina	19	12	21	20		23	16					
Bulgaria	40	9	20	24	14	28	17	19	7	12	11	7
Croatia	17	18	16	16	7	9	4	3	2	2	2	2
Cyprus	3	4	3	3	1	3	3	2	2	2	2	2
Czechia	150	95	67	92	64	58	19	37	45	52	55	49
Denmark	7	9	8	14	2	4	6	3	3	3	3	3
Estonia	7	7	9	9	5	9	7	4	5	5	5	5
Finland	35	21	17	32	9	14		2	5	5	2	5
France	331	239	299	361	37	80	16	40	45	46	45	46
Germany	380	321	277	589	91	75	60	96	89	89	89	89
Greece	37	22	32	33	4	18	19	8	4	4	4	4
Hungary	23	12	18	19	16	18	21	15	10	10		10
Iceland	12	9	1	11		22	1					
Ireland	66	61	17	33	5	11	3	2	5	5	5	5
Italy	562	324	344	616	163	198	183	239	139	138	132	131
Kosovo	12	12	11	11		11	11					
Latvia	8	5	8	7	5	4	3	4	3	3	3	3
Liechtenstein												
Lithuania	16	13	13	17	5	14	9	5	5	5	5	5
Luxembourg	7	4	5	142	2	4	2	1	2	2	2	2
Malta	5	5	4	5	2	4	2	2	2	2		2
Montenegro	1	1	1	5		2	4					
Netherlands	71	53	45	75	3	13	6	11	2	2	2	2
North Macedonia	11	12	17	17		17	12					
Norway	53	49	12	44	7	5	1	8	4	4	2	4
Poland	252	137	97	132	169	86	54	61	57	57	56	57
Portugal	59	20	50	63		21	14	8				
Romania	79	57	28	25	10	30	15	3	17	22	25	23
Serbia	17	12	6	13		13	14		2	2	2	2
Slovakia	48	47	24	39	21	20	17	14	12	12	12	12
Slovenia	21	18	11	11	5	3	1	3	5	5	5	5
Spain	467	308	432	519	87	399	217	123	105	104	108	105
Sweden	61	44	43	93	6	39	2	9	5	5	5	5
Switzerland	30	8	30	31	9	8	9	3	10	13	13	10
Türkiye	251	106	132	163		205	117					

The countries included in this report and that, therefore, appear in Figure 1, are those with the obligation to report data under the AAQD or that have voluntarily reported data. These countries are the EU-27 (Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Croatia, Cyprus, Czechia, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Latvia, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Malta,

the Netherlands, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain and Sweden); the five other member countries of the EEA (Iceland, Liechtenstein, Norway, Switzerland and Türkiye) that, together with the EU-27 form the EEA-32; the six EEA's cooperating countries from the Western Balkans (Albania, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Kosovo under UN Security Council Resolution 1244/99, Montenegro, North Macedonia and Serbia) that, together with the EEA-32 form the EEA-38; and the voluntary reporting country of Andorra.

The air quality data are stored at the EEA's e-reporting database ⁽³⁾. Therefore, this is the source for all maps and figures in the report.

1.1 Particulate matter

For PM₁₀, concentrations above the EU daily limit value (50 µg/m³) were registered at 12 % of the reporting stations. These stations were in 12 countries in EU-27 and in 6 other reporting countries. For PM_{2.5}, concentrations above the EU annual limit value (25 µg/m³) were registered at 1 % of the reporting stations. These stations were in 1 countries in EU-27 and in 4 other reporting countries.

The long-term World Health Organization air quality guideline (WHO AQG) level for PM₁₀ (15 µg/m³) was exceeded at 63 % of the stations in 27 countries of the EU-27 and 7 other reporting countries. The long-term WHO AQG level for PM_{2.5} (5 µg/m³) was exceeded at 93 % of the stations located in 26 countries of the EU-27 and 9 other reporting countries.

All Member States had met the exposure concentration obligation that was set under the Ambient Air Quality Directive to be attained as of 2015. The exposure concentration obligation reflects exposure of the population to fine particles and required that by 2015 exposure of the general population to PM_{2.5} averaged over the previous 3-year period should not exceed 20 µg/m³. The national exposure reduction target was met for all reporting countries.

1.2 Ozone

17 % of stations registered concentrations above the EU target value for O₃ (120 µg/m³), averaged over three years, for the protection of human health. These stations were located in 16 countries of the EU-27 and 5 other reporting countries. The long-term EU objective (120 µg/m³) was met in only 23 % of the stations. The short-term WHO AQG level for O₃ (100 µg/m³) was exceeded in 91 % of all the reporting stations, and concentrations above the long-term WHO AQG level for O₃ (60 µg/m³) were registered in 97 % of all reporting stations.

³https://discomap.eea.europa.eu/App/AQViewer/index.html?fqn=Airquality_Dissemin.b2g.AirQualityStatistics

1.3 Nitrogen dioxide

Around 2 % of all the reporting stations recorded concentrations above the EU annual limit value for NO₂ (40 µg/m³). These stations were located in 6 countries of the EU-27 and 2 other reporting country. 66 % of concentrations above this limit value were observed at traffic stations.

On the contrary, 67 % of stations, located in 27 countries of the EU-27 and 10 other reporting countries reported concentrations above the WHO AQG level of 10 µg/m³.

1.4 Benzo[a]pyrene

20 % of the stations reported annual mean concentrations above 1.0 ng/m³. They were located in 12 countries in EU-27.

1.5 Sulphur dioxide, carbon monoxide, benzene and toxic metals

For SO₂, regarding the EU daily limit value (125 µg/m³), concentrations above were registered at 1.1 % of the reporting stations. These stations were in 3 other reporting countries . On the other hand, concerning the daily WHO AQG level (40 µg/m³), 5 % of all reporting SO₂ stations measured SO₂ concentrations above. These stations were located in 7 countries of the EU-27 and 5 other reporting countries .

The EU limit value for CO (10 mg/m³), which is the same as the 8-hour WHO AQG level, was exceeded at 0.1 % of the stations. These stations were in 1 country of the EU-27.

Concentrations above the EU limit value for C₆H₆ (5 µg/m³) were not observed at any stations.

0.8 % of stations registered concentrations above the EU target value for As (6 ng/m³). These stations were located in 4 countries of the EU-27. For Cd, concentrations above the EU target value (5 ng/m³) were not observed at any stations . The EU target value for Ni (20 ng/m³) was exceeded at 0.6 % of the stations. These stations were located in 3 countries of the EU-27. Pb concentrations above the limit value (0.5 µg/m³) were measured at 0.2 % of the stations located in 1 country of the EU-27.

1.6 Editorial note

Values in Table 4 in Annex 1 are considered outliers and were not taken into account for the analysis presented in this report.

On 20 November 2024, the revised Directive (EU) 2024/2881 (EU, 2024) on ambient air quality and cleaner air for Europe was published and it entered into force on 10 December 2024. It sets new or revised air quality standards to be reached by 1 January 2030. The main analysis in this report is done against the AQ standards defined in the 2004 and 2008 AAQD (EU, 2008, 2024), which are the ones currently applicable. Annex 2 benchmarks the situation in year 2024 with respect to some of the new and/or revised AQ standards, as an analysis of the 'distance to target' from the 2024 status.

2 Introduction

The 2024 *Status report of air quality in Europe* presents summarized information on the air quality data reported as measurements data under the 2025 September reporting cycle (validated assessment data for 2024, deadline of submission 30 September 2025). This report aims at informing on the 2024 status of ambient air quality in Europe and on progress towards meeting the air quality standards established for the protection of health in the Ambient Air Quality Directives (EU, 2004, 2008) (Table 1) and the World Health Organization air quality guideline levels (WHO, 2000, 2006, 2021) (Table 2)⁽⁴⁾.

This report builds on the former EEA “Air quality in Europe report” (EEA, 2020) content, figures and maps regarding the status of monitored air quality in Europe. It provides:

- a European overview of the 2024 monitoring stations reported, and of their concentrations in relation to the EU legal standards set in the 2004 and 2008 EU Ambient Air Quality Directives (EU, 2004, 2008) and WHO AQG levels for each pollutant;
- a map with the 2024 concentrations at station level for each pollutant;
- a boxplot graph summarizing for each country the range of concentrations (highlighting the lowest, highest, average and the 25 and 75 percentiles) for PM₁₀, PM_{2.5}, NO₂, O₃ and BaP.

Furthermore, it provides:

- maps with the situation at station level for the previous three years. In this way, any significant change in the spatial distribution of the values above the set thresholds in the legends can be observed;
- heatmaps with the evolution of the mean and the maximum measured concentrations at country level since 2000 (or since when available).

⁴Nevertheless, in this report the following standards and guideline levels are not analysed: information and alert thresholds for O₃, alert threshold for NO₂, and alert threshold for SO₂ in Table 1; and hourly air quality guideline level for NO₂, 10 minutes air quality guideline level for SO₂, and hourly air quality guideline level for CO in Table 2.

Table 1: Air quality standards for the protection of health, as given in the EU 2004 and 2008 Ambient Air Quality Directives

Pollutant	Averaging period	Legal nature and concentration	Comments
PM ₁₀	1 day	Limit value: 50 µg/m ³	Not to be exceeded on more than 35 days per year
	Calendar year	Limit value: 40 µg/m ³	
PM _{2,5}	Calendar year	Limit value: 25 µg/m ³	Stage 1
		Indicative limit value: 20 µg/m ³	Stage 2: indicative limit value to be reviewed by the Commission in 2013. It remained unchanged after that revision
		Exposure concentration obligation: 20 µg/m ³	Average Exposure Indicator (AEI) ^(a) in 2015 (2013-2015 average)
		National Exposure reduction target: 0-20 percentage reduction in exposure	AEI ^(a) in 2020, the percentage reduction depends on the initial AEI
O ₃	Maximum daily 8-hour mean	Target value: 120 µg/m ³	Not to be exceeded on more than 25 days/year, averaged over 3 years ^(b)
		Long term objective: 120 µg/m ³	
	1 hour	Information threshold: 180 µg/m ³ Alert threshold: 240 µg/m ³	
NO ₂	1 hour	Limit value: 200 µg/m ³	Not to be exceeded on more than 18 hours per year
		Alert threshold: 400 µg/m ³	To be measured over 3 consecutive hours over 100 km ² or an entire zone
	Calendar year	Limit value: 40 µg/m ³	
BaP	Calendar year	Target value: 1 ng/m ³	Measured as content in PM ₁₀
SO ₂	1 hour	Limit value: 350 µg/m ³	Not to be exceeded on more than 24 hours per year
		Alert threshold: 500 µg/m ³	To be measured over 3 consecutive hours over 100 km ² or an entire zone
	1 day	Limit value: 125 µg/m ³	Not to be exceeded on more than 3 days per year
CO	Maximum daily 8-hour mean	Limit value: 10 mg/m ³	
C ₆ H ₆	Calendar year	Limit value: 5 µg/m ³	
Pb	Calendar year	Limit value: 0.5 µg/m ³	Measured as content in PM ₁₀
As	Calendar year	Target value: 6 ng/m ³	Measured as content in PM ₁₀
Cd	Calendar year	Target value: 5 ng/m ³	Measured as content in PM ₁₀
Ni	Calendar year	Target value: 20 ng/m ³	Measured as content in PM ₁₀

Notes:

^a AEI: based upon measurements in urban background locations established for this purpose by the Member States, assessed as a 3-year running annual mean.

^b In the context of this report, both the maximum daily 8-hour means in 2024 and the average over the period 2022 - 2024 are considered.

Sources:

EU (2004, 2008).

Table 2: WHO air quality guideline (AQG) levels and estimated reference levels (RL) ^(a)

Pollutant	Averaging period	AQG	RL	Comments
PM ₁₀	1 day	45 µg/m ³		99th percentile (3-4 exceedance days per year). Updated 2021 guideline
	Calendar year	15 µg/m ³		Updated 2021 guideline
PM _{2.5}	1 day	15 µg/m ³		99th percentile (3-4 exceedance days per year). Updated 2021 guideline
	Calendar year	5 µg/m ³		Updated 2021 guideline
O ₃	Maximum daily 8-hour mean	100 µg/m ³		99th percentile (3-4 exceedance days per year). Updated 2021 guideline
	Peak season ^(b)	60 µg/m ³		New 2021 guideline
NO ₂	1 hour	200 µg/m ³		
	1 day	25 µg/m ³		99th percentile (3-4 exceedance days per year). New 2021 guideline
	Calendar year	10 µg/m ³		Updated 2021 guideline
BaP	Calendar year		0.12 ng/m ³	
SO ₂	10 minutes	500 µg/m ³		
	1 day	40 µg/m ³		99th percentile (3-4 exceedance days per year). Updated 2021 guideline
CO	1 hour	30 mg/m ³		
	Maximum daily 8-hour mean	10 mg/m ³		
	1 day	4 mg/m ³		99th percentile (3-4 exceedance days per year). New 2021 guideline
C ₆ H ₆	Calendar year		1.7 µg/m ³	
Pb	Calendar year	0.5 µg/m ³		
As	Calendar year		6.6 ng/m ³	
Cd	Calendar year	5 ng/m ³ ^(c)		
Ni	Calendar year		25 ng/m ³	

Notes:

^a As WHO has not set an AQG level for BaP, C₆H₆, As and Ni, the RL was estimated assuming an acceptable risk of additional lifetime cancer risk of approximately 1 in 100 000.

^b Average of daily maximum 8-hour mean concentration in the six consecutive months with the highest six-month running average O₃ concentration.

^c AQG set to prevent any further increase of Cd in agricultural soil, likely to increase the dietary intake of future generations.

Sources:

WHO (2000, 2006, 2021).

Box 1.1 Classification of monitoring stations and criteria used for the assessment

Fixed sampling points in Europe are situated at different types of stations following rules for macro- and micro-scale siting. Briefly, depending on the predominant emission sources, stations are classified as follows:

- traffic stations: located in close proximity to a single major road;
- industrial stations: located in close proximity to an industrial area or an industrial source;
- background stations: where pollution levels are representative of the average exposure of the general population or vegetation.

Depending on the distribution/density of buildings, the area surrounding the station is classified as follows:

- urban: continuously built-up urban area;
- suburban: largely built-up urban area;
- rural: all other areas.

In general, for the pollutants considered in this report, monitoring stations have to fulfil the criterion of reporting more than 75 % of valid data out of all the possible data in a year to be included in this assessment. The 2008 EU Ambient Air Quality Directive sets, for compliance purposes, the objective of a minimum data capture of 90 % for monitoring stations, but, for assessment purposes, a coverage of 75 % allows more stations to be taken into account without a significant increase in monitoring uncertainties. For benzene, As, Cd, Ni and BaP, the general amount of valid data is 13% (according to the air quality objectives for indicative measurements). The exceptions to the general rule are PM and lead random fixed measurements, for which the required amount of valid data for the analysis is 13 %. Reporting stations not fulfilling the minimum data coverage could be found at the [Annual AQ statistics table](#).

Measurement data are rounded following the general recommendations under (EU, 2011). The number of considered decimals are indicated in the legend of the corresponding maps.

The assessments do not account for the fact that the 2004 and 2008 EU Ambient Air Quality Directives (EU, 2004, 2008) provide Member States with the possibility of subtracting contributions to the measured concentrations from natural sources and winter road sanding/salting under specific circumstances.

3 Status of particulate matter ambient air concentrations

3.1 Status of PM₁₀ concentrations

The EEA received PM₁₀ data for 2024, with sufficient valid measurements (a general minimum coverage of 75 % and of 13 % for fixed random measurements) from 3364 stations for the calculation of annual mean concentrations and from 3344 stations in relation to the daily limit value. The stations were located in all the reporting countries shown in Figure 1.

Twelve countries in EU-27, and six other reporting countries reported PM₁₀ concentrations above the EU daily limit value of 50 µg/m³ (Figure 2). This was the case for 12 % (417) of reporting stations. In total, 97 % of those stations were either urban (87 %) or suburban (10 %). The stricter value of the WHO AQG level for PM₁₀ daily mean (45 µg/m³) was exceeded at 62 % (2089) of the stations in all the reporting countries, except in Denmark, Luxembourg and Switzerland (Figure 8).

Concentrations above the PM₁₀ annual limit value (40 µg/m³) were monitored in 4 % (133 stations) of all the reporting stations, located in 3 countries in EU-27, and 5 other reporting countries. The stricter value of the WHO AQG level for PM₁₀ annual mean (15 µg/m³) was exceeded at 63 % (2127) of the stations in all the reporting countries, except in Andorra, Iceland and Switzerland (Figure 5).

Figure 2: Map and boxplot of PM₁₀ concentrations in 2024 - daily limit value

Note: Observed concentrations of PM₁₀ in 2024. The possibility of subtracting contributions to the measured concentrations from natural sources and winter road sanding/salting has not been considered. The map shows the 90.4 percentile of the PM₁₀ daily mean concentrations, representing the 36th highest value in a complete series. It is related to the PM₁₀ daily limit value, allowing 35 exceedances of the 50 µg/m³ threshold over 1 year. The last two colour categories indicate stations with concentrations above this daily limit value. Only stations with more than 75 % of valid data, and more than 13 % in the case of fixed random measurements, have been included in the map.

Note: The graph is based, for each country, on the 90.4 percentile of daily mean concentration values corresponding to the 36th highest daily mean in a complete time series. For each country, the number of stations considered for 2024 (in brackets) are given. The boxplot represents the lowest (bottom of the whisker), highest (top of the whisker) and average (black dot) 90.4 percentile values (in µg/m³). The rectangles mark the 25th and 75th percentiles. At 25 % of the stations, levels are below the 25th percentile; at 25 % of the stations, concentrations are above the 75th percentile. The daily limit value set by EU legislation is marked by the horizontal line. The graph should be read in relation to the above map, as a country's situation depends on the number of stations considered.

The highest value in the boxplot, Türkiye (214 µg/m³), has not been included in the graph for representation purposes.

Figure 3 shows the maps of the 90.4 percentile of PM₁₀ daily mean concentrations (equivalent to the PM₁₀ daily limit value) for four years. In this way, any significant change in the spatial distribution of the values above the set thresholds in the legends can be observed. These maps are based on officially reported validated data on the central data repository (CDR).

Figure 3: Maps of PM₁₀ concentrations (daily limit value) for the last 4 years

Heatmaps with the evolution from 2000 of the mean (top) and the maximum (bottom) 90.4 percentile of PM₁₀ daily mean concentrations at country level are shown in figure 4. In this way, the evolution along years of the average and maximum measured concentration levels can be seen for each country. Note that meteorological variability has a considerable impact on year-to-year changes in ambient air concentrations of air pollutants (EEA, 2020).

Figure 4: Evolution of mean (top) and maximum (bottom) 90.4 percentile of PM₁₀ daily mean concentrations (daily limit value) per country from 2000

Note: It is important to note that the figure is not based on a consistent set of stations. The number, location and classification of the stations included may vary from year to year.

Figure 5: Map and boxplot of PM₁₀ concentrations in 2024 - annual limit value

Note: Observed concentrations of PM₁₀ in 2024. The possibility of subtracting contributions to the measured concentrations from natural sources and winter road sanding/salting has not been considered. The last two colour categories indicate stations reporting concentrations above the EU annual limit value (40 µg/m³). The first colour category indicate stations reporting values below the WHO AQG level for PM₁₀ (15 µg/m³). Only stations with more than 75 % of valid data, and more than 13 % in the case of fixed random measurements, have been included in the map.

Note: The graph is based on annual mean concentration values. For each country, the number of stations considered for 2024 (in brackets) are given. The boxplot represents the lowest (bottom of the whisker), highest (top of the whisker) and average (black dot) annual mean values (in µg/m³). The rectangles mark the 25th and 75th percentiles. At 25 % of the stations, levels are below the 25th percentile; at 25 % of the stations, concentrations are above the 75th percentile. The annual limit value set by EU legislation is marked by the upper continuous horizontal line. The WHO AQG level is marked by the lower dashed horizontal line. The graph should be read in relation to the above map, as a country's situation depends on the number of stations considered.

Figure 6 shows the maps of PM₁₀ annual mean concentrations at station level for the last four years. In this way, any significant change in the spatial distribution of the values above the set thresholds in the legends can be observed. These maps are based on officially reported validated data (CDR).

Figure 6: Maps of PM₁₀ concentrations (annual limit value) for the last 4 years

Heatmaps with the evolution from 2000 of the mean (top) and the maximum (bottom) annual mean PM₁₀ concentrations at country level are shown in figure 7. In this way, the evolution along years of the average and maximum measured concentration levels can be seen for each country. Note that meteorological variability has a considerable impact on year-to-year changes in ambient air concentrations of air pollutants (EEA, 2020).

Figure 7: Evolution of mean (top) and maximum (bottom) PM₁₀ annual mean concentrations (annual limit value) per country from 2000

Note: It is important to note that the figure is not based on a consistent set of stations. The number, location and classification of the stations included may vary from year to year.

Figure 8: Map of PM₁₀ concentrations in 2024 - daily WHO AQG level

Note: Observed concentrations of PM₁₀ in 2024. The map shows the 99 percentile of the PM₁₀ daily mean concentrations, equivalent to 3–4 exceedance days per year, according to the definition of the daily WHO AQG level (45 µg/m³). The first colour category indicates stations with concentrations below this AQG level. Only stations with more than 75 % of valid data, and more than 13 % in the case of fixed random measurements, have been included in the map.

Figure 9 shows the maps of the 99 percentile of PM₁₀ daily mean concentrations (equivalent to the WHO AQG level for PM₁₀ daily mean level) for the last four years. In this way, any significant change in the spatial distribution of the values above the set thresholds in the legends can be observed. These maps are based on officially reported validated data (CDR).

Figure 9: Maps of PM₁₀ concentrations (daily WHO AQG level) for the last 4 years

Heatmaps with the evolution from 2013 of the mean (top) and the maximum (bottom) 99 percentile of PM₁₀ daily mean concentrations at country level are shown in figure 10. In this way, the evolution along years of the average and maximum measured concentration levels can be seen for each country. Note that meteorological variability has a considerable impact on year-to-year changes in ambient air concentrations of air pollutants (EEA, 2020).

Figure 10: Evolution of mean (top) and maximum (bottom) 99 percentile of PM₁₀ daily mean concentrations (daily WHO AQG level) per country from 2013

Note: It is important to note that the figure is not based on a consistent set of stations. The number, location and classification of the stations included may vary from year to year.

3.2 Status of PM_{2.5} concentrations

Regarding PM_{2.5}, data with a general minimum coverage of 75 %, and of 13 % for fixed random stations, of valid data were received from 2223 stations for the calculation of annual mean concentrations and from 2208 stations in relation to the short-term WHO AQG level. These stations were located in all the reporting countries shown in Figure 1.

The PM_{2.5} concentrations were higher than the EU annual limit value (25 µg/m³) in one countries in EU-27 and four other reporting countries (Figure 11). These concentrations above the limit value were registered in 1 % of all the reporting stations and occurred primarily (95 % of cases) in urban (91 %) or suburban (4 %) areas.

The WHO AQG level for PM_{2.5} annual mean (5 µg/m³) was exceeded at 93 % of the stations, located in 35 of the 37 countries reporting PM_{2.5} data (Figure 11). Estonia and Iceland did not report any concentrations above the WHO AQG level for PM_{2.5}.

The WHO AQG level for PM_{2.5} daily mean (15 µg/m³), expressed as percentile 99, it was exceeded at 96 % (2119 stations) of the stations in all the reporting countries (Figure 14).

Figure 11: Map and boxplot of PM_{2.5} concentrations in 2024 - annual limit value

Note: Observed concentrations of PM_{2.5} in 2024. The possibility of subtracting contributions to the measured concentrations from natural sources has not been considered. The last two colour categories indicate stations reporting concentrations above the EU indicative annual limit value (20 µg/m³) or the EU annual limit value (25 µg/m³). The first colour category indicates stations reporting values below the WHO AQG level for PM_{2.5} (5 µg/m³). Only stations with more than 75 % of valid data, and more than 13% in the case of fixed random measurements, have been included in the map.

Note: The graph is based on annual mean concentration values. For each country, the number of stations considered for 2024 (in brackets) are given. The boxplot represents the lowest (bottom of the whisker), highest (top of the whisker) and average (black dot) annual mean values (in µg/m³). The rectangles mark the 25th and 75th percentiles. At 25 % of the stations, levels are below the 25th percentile; at 25 % of the stations, concentrations are above the 75th percentile. The annual limit value and the indicative annual limit value set by EU legislation are marked by the upper continuous horizontal lines at 25 and 20, respectively. The WHO AQG level is marked by the lower dashed horizontal line. The graph should be read in relation to the above map, as a country's situation depends on the number of stations considered.

Figure 12 shows the maps of measured PM_{2.5} annual mean concentrations for the last four years. In this way, any significant change in the spatial distribution of the values above the set thresholds in the legends can be observed. These maps are based on officially reported validated data (CDR).

Figure 12: Maps of PM_{2.5} concentrations (annual limit value) for the last 4 years

Heatmaps with the evolution from 2000 of the mean (top) and the maximum (bottom) PM_{2.5} annual mean concentrations at country level are shown in figure 13. In this way, the evolution along years of the average and maximum measured concentration levels can be seen for each country. Note that meteorological variability has a considerable impact on year-to-year changes in ambient air concentrations of air pollutants (EEA, 2020).

Figure 13: Evolution of mean (top) and maximum (bottom) PM_{2.5} annual mean concentrations (annual limit value) per country from 2000

Note: It is important to note that the figure is not based on a consistent set of stations. The number, location and classification of the stations included may vary from year to year.

Figure 14: Map of PM_{2.5} concentrations in 2024 - daily WHO AQG level

Note: Observed concentrations of PM_{2.5} in 2024. The map shows the 99 percentile of the PM_{2.5} daily mean concentrations, equivalent to 3–4 exceedance days per year, according to the definition of the daily WHO AQG level (15 µg/m³). The first colour category indicates stations with concentrations below this AQG level. Only stations with more than 75 % of valid data, and more than 13 % in the case of fixed random measurements, have been included in the map.

Figure 15 shows the maps of the 99 percentile of PM_{2.5} daily mean concentrations (equivalent to the WHO AQG level for PM_{2.5} daily mean level) for the last four years. In this way, any significant change in the spatial distribution of the values above the set thresholds in the legends can be observed. These maps are based on officially reported validated data (CDR).

Figure 15: Maps of PM_{2.5} concentrations (daily WHO AQG level) for the last 4 years

Heatmaps with the evolution from 2013 of the mean (top) and the maximum (bottom) 99 percentile of PM_{2.5} daily mean concentrations at country level are shown in figure 16. In this way, the evolution along years of the average and maximum measured concentration levels can be seen for each country. Note that meteorological variability has a considerable impact on year-to-year changes in ambient air concentrations of air pollutants (EEA, 2020).

Figure 16: Evolution of mean (top) and maximum (bottom) 99 percentile of PM_{2.5} daily mean concentrations (daily WHO AQG level) per country from 2013

Note: It is important to note that the figure is not based on a consistent set of stations. The number, location and classification of the stations included may vary from year to year.

3.3 PM_{2.5} average exposure indicator

The Ambient Air Quality Directive (EU, 2008) also sets two additional targets for PM_{2.5}, the exposure concentration obligation (ECO) and the national exposure reduction target (NERT) (Table 1). Both targets are based on the average exposure indicator (AEI), calculated at national level. The AEI is an average of concentration levels (over a 3-year period) measured at urban background stations (representative of general urban population exposure) selected for this purpose by every national authority. The reference year for the AEI is 2010 (average 2008-2010), but the Ambient Air Quality Directive offered two additional alternatives when data are not available for 2008: (1) an alternative AEI 2010, with a 2-year average (2009 and 2010) instead of the 3-year average; or (2) the AEI 2011 (average 2009-2011). The exception is Croatia for which 2015 is the AEI reference year (average 2013-2015). The data presented here are analysed with reference to the official AEI reported by each country and stored in EEA's vocabulary ⁽⁵⁾ and presented in Table 5 in the Annex.

Figure 17 assesses PM_{2.5} levels against the ECO threshold. It shows the AEI reported for 2024 (average 2022-2024) and the situation in relation to the ECO. The bars show the AEI 2024 as reported by countries under data flow G (Information on the attainment of environmental objectives) according to Article 12 of IPR Decision 2011/850/EU, while the dots show the 3-year (2022-2024) average concentrations from measurements at all urban and suburban background stations with 75 % data coverage. This calculation, covering the urban and suburban background stations, has been used in previous *Air quality in Europe* reports as an approximation of the AEI and is presented here for comparison with the information presented in those reports. The calculation using reported urban and suburban background stations is also made for the rest of the non-EU countries.

In Figure 17, the vertical line represents the ECO threshold, set at 20 µg/m³. For those countries whose bars are to the right of the vertical line, the AEI is above the ECO (based on reported information in data-flow G). For those countries whose dots are to the right of the vertical line, the 3 year average calculated from reported urban and suburban background stations is above the ECO.

⁵<https://dd.eionet.europa.eu/vocabulary/aq/exposurereductiontarget/view>.

Figure 17: Average exposure indicator in 2024 and exposure concentration obligation

Note: The bars show the average exposure indicator (AEI) calculated in 2024 (averages 2022–2024) as reported by countries under data flow G (Information on the attainment of environmental objectives) according to Article 12 of IPR Decision 2011/850/EU. The dots show the 3 year (2022–2024) average of all urban and suburban background PM2.5 concentrations (for stations with at least 75 % of data coverage) in all reporting countries, to facilitate comparison with information provided in previous Air quality in Europe reports. The vertical line represents the exposure concentration obligation (ECO) for the countries in EU–27, set at 20 µg/m³, to be achieved as of 2015.

Figure 18 shows the situation per country in relation to the NERT. The total stacked bar (both blue and orange parts) represents the initial baseline AEI for 2010 or 2011 as reported by each country expressed in $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ (see Table 5 in Annex). The blue part is the latest reported AEI for 2024, as it can also be seen in figure 17 (if a country has not reported data for the year of analysis, only the orange bar will be shown). The triangles indicate the NERT level to be attained from 2020 onwards. Figure 18 shows those countries that have reduced their AEI below their corresponding NERT, estimated from their initial AEI baseline, (those who have reported data, and therefore have blue part, and whose triangles is over the orange bar) and those that did not (triangles over the blue part of the bar).

Figure 18: Reduction in AEI 2024 in relation to initial AEI (either 2010 or 2011) and distance to the national exposure reduction target

Note: The total stacked bar indicate the initial baseline AEI for 2010 or 2011 (AEI 2015 in the case of Croatia, see the main text).
 Triangles indicate the NERT to be met in 2024 applying the percentage reduction to the AEI baseline.
 If the triangle is over the orange part of the stack bar, the NERT was achieved in 2024,
 if the triangle is over the blue part of the bar, the NERT is not met.

4 Status of ozone ambient air concentrations

Data for O₃ were reported from 2180 stations for the calculation of EU standards, from 2180 stations in relation to the short-term WHO AQG level, and from 2053 stations for the long-term WHO AQG level. These stations were located in all the reporting countries shown in Figure 1. 17 countries in EU-27 and 6 other reporting countries registered concentrations above the O₃ target value threshold (120 µg/m³) more than 25 times this year (Figure 19). In total, 16 % of all stations reporting O₃ showed concentrations above the target value threshold for the protection of human health. Furthermore, the 2022-2024 average of the annual number of days with maximum daily 8-hour means above 120 µg/m³ was higher than 25 (that is, above the target value) in 328 stations (17% of the total) in 16 countries of the EU-27 and 5 other reporting countries (Figure 22). In addition, only 23 % (492) of all stations fulfilled the long-term objective (120 µg/m³). 86 % of the stations with values above the long-term objective were background stations.

9 % (196) of all stations and only 25 of the 547 reported rural background stations had values below the short-term WHO AQG value for O₃ (100 µg/m³) (Figure 25), set for the protection of human health. The long-term, peak season⁶, WHO AQG level (60 µg/m³) was exceeded in 97 % (2000) of all stations located in 27 countries in EU-27 and 7 other reporting countries. Only 3 of the 520 reported rural background stations had values below this AQG level (Figure 28).

⁶The peak season is calculated for each station as the average of daily maximum 8-hour mean O₃ concentration in the six consecutive months with the highest six-month running-average O₃ concentration. That means that, for each station, twelve 6-months running averages of the daily 8-h max are calculated (1 August YY-1 to 31 January YY, ..., 1 January YY to 30 June YY, ..., 1 July YY to 31 December YY) and the maximum of those 12 values is selected as the peak season concentration. Please check also Data Dictionary - Vocabulary (<https://dd.eionet.europa.eu/vocabularyconcept/aq/aggregationprocess/P1Y-maxP6M-P8H-dmax/view?vocabularyFolder.workingCopy=false&facet=HTML+Representation>).

Figure 19: Map and boxplot of O₃ concentrations in 2024

Note: Observed concentrations of O₃ in 2024. The map shows the 93.2 percentile of the O₃ maximum daily 8–hour mean, representing the 26th highest value in a complete series. It is related to the O₃ target value. At sites marked with the last two colour categories, the 26th highest daily O₃ concentrations were above the 120 µg/m³ threshold, implying values above the target value threshold. Please note that the legal definition of the target value considers not only 1 year but the average over 3 years. Only stations with more than 75 % of valid data have been included in the map.

Note: The graph is based, for each country, on the 93.2 percentile of the maximum daily 8–hour mean concentration values, corresponding to the 26th highest daily maximum of the running 8–hour mean in a complete time series. For each country, the number of stations considered for 2024 (in brackets) are given. The boxplot represents the lowest (bottom of the whisker), highest (top of the whisker) and average (black dot) values (in µg/m³). The rectangles mark the 25th and 75th percentiles. At 25 % of the stations, levels are below the 25th percentile; at 25 % of the stations, concentrations are above the 75th percentile. The target value threshold set by the EU legislation is marked by the horizontal line. Please note that the legal definition of the target value considers not only 1 year but the average over 3 years. The graph should be read in relation to the above map, as a country's situation depends on the number of stations considered.

The highest value in the boxplot, Bosnia and Herzegovina (269 µg/m³), has not been included in the graph for representation purposes.

Figure 20 shows the maps of the observed 93.2 percentile of the O₃ maximum daily 8-hour mean concentrations (O₃ target value) for the last four years. In this way, any significant change in the spatial distribution of the values above the set thresholds in the legends can be observed. These maps are based on officially reported validated data (CDR).

Figure 20: Maps of O₃ concentrations (related to the target value) for the last 4 years

Note: Please be aware that the TV considers the average over 3 years and the maps only show the situation for one specific year. To check the situation with the TV please see Figure 22

Heatmaps with the evolution from 2000 of the mean (top) and the maximum (bottom) O₃ concentrations (93.2 percentile of the maximum daily 8-hour mean concentration, target value) at country level are shown in figure 21. In this way, the evolution along years of the average and maximum measured concentration levels can be seen for each country. Note that meteorological variability has a considerable impact on year-to-year changes in ambient air concentrations of air pollutants (EEA, 2020), especially for O₃ as higher ambient air temperature leads to enhanced photochemical reactions and O₃ formation.

Figure 21: Evolution of mean (top) and maximum (bottom) O₃ concentrations (93.2 percentile of the maximum daily 8-hour mean concentration, related to the target value) per country from 2000

Note: It is important to note that the figure is not based on a consistent set of stations. The number, location and classification of the stations included may vary from year to year.

Figure 22: Map and boxplot of O₃ concentrations in 2024 - target value human health

Note: The map shows the 2022–2024 average of the annual number of days with maximum daily 8–hour means above 120 µg/m³. The last two categories of the legend indicate stations with this average about 25, meaning above the O₃ target value for the protection of human health.

Note: The graph is based, for each country, on the 2022–2024 average of the annual number of days with maximum daily 8–hour means above 120 µg/m³. For each country, the number of stations considered for the three years (in brackets) are given. The boxplot represents the lowest (bottom of the whisker), highest (top of the whisker) and average (black dot) values (in number of days). The rectangles mark the 25th and 75th percentiles. At 25 % of the stations, the three–years average number of days are below the 25th percentile; at 25 % of the stations, the three–years average number of days are above the 75th percentile. The target value set by the EU legislation is marked by the horizontal line. The graph should be read in relation to the above map, as a country’s situation depends on the number of stations considered.

Figure 23 shows the maps of three-years average of the annual number of days with maximum daily 8-hour means above 120 µg/m³ for the last four years. In this way, the evolution

of the situation against the O₃ target value to protect human health can be observed. These maps are based on officially reported validated data (CDR).

Figure 23: Maps of the O₃ situation in relation to the target value for protection of human health for the last 4 years

Note: The map shows the 2022–2024 average of the annual number of days with maximum daily 8–hour means above 120 µg/m³. The last two categories of the legend indicate stations with this average about 25, meaning above the O₃ target value for the protection of human health.

Heatmaps with the evolution from 2015 of the mean (top) and the maximum (bottom) three-years average of the number of days when the O₃ maximum daily 8-hour mean concentrations were above 120 µg/m³ at country level are shown in figure 24. Note that meteorological variability has a considerable impact on year-to-year changes in ambient air concentrations of air pollutants (EEA, 2020), especially for O₃ as higher ambient air temperature leads to enhanced photochemical reactions and O₃ formation.

Figure 24: Evolution of mean (top) and maximum (bottom) of the three-years average of the number of days when the O₃ maximum daily 8-hour mean concentrations were above 120 µg/m³ per country from 2015

Note: It is important to note that the figure is not based on a consistent set of stations. The number, location and classification of the stations included may vary from year to year.

Figure 25: Map of O₃ concentrations in 2024 - short-term WHO AQG level

Note: Observed concentrations of O₃ in 2024. The map shows the 99 percentile of the O₃ maximum daily 8-hour mean concentrations, equivalent to 3–4 exceedance days per year, according to the definition of the short-term WHO AQG level (100 µg/m³). The first colour category indicates stations with concentrations below this AQG level. Only stations with more than 75 % of valid data have been included in the map.

Figure 26 shows the maps of the 99 percentile of the O₃ maximum daily 8-hour mean concentrations (equivalent to the short-term WHO AQG level) for the last four years. In this way, any significant change in the spatial distribution of the values above the set thresholds in the legends can be observed. These maps are based on officially reported validated data (CDR).

Figure 26: Maps of O₃ concentrations (short-term WHO AQG level) for the last 4 years

Heatmaps with the evolution from 2013 of the mean (top) and the maximum (bottom) 99 percentile of the O₃ maximum daily 8-hour mean concentrations at country level are shown in figure 27. In this way, the evolution along years of the average and maximum measured concentration levels can be seen for each country. Note that meteorological variability has a considerable impact on year-to-year changes in ambient air concentrations of air pollutants (EEA, 2020).

Figure 27: Evolution of mean (top) and maximum (bottom) 99 percentile of the O₃ maximum daily 8-hour mean concentrations per country from 2013

Note: It is important to note that the figure is not based on a consistent set of stations. The number, location and classification of the stations included may vary from year to year.

Figure 28: Map of peak season O₃ concentrations in 2024

Note: Observed concentrations of O₃ in 2024. The map shows the average of the daily maximum 8-hour mean O₃ concentration in the six consecutive months with the highest six-month running-average O₃ concentration. The first colour category represents stations fulfilling the peak season O₃ AQG level. Only stations with more than 75 % of valid data have been included in the map.

Figure 29 shows the maps of the peak season O₃ concentrations (equivalent to the long-term WHO AQG level) for the last four years. In this way, any significant change in the spatial distribution of the values above the set thresholds in the legends can be observed. These maps are based on officially reported validated data (CDR).

Figure 29: Maps of peak season O₃ concentrations for the last 4 years

Heatmaps with the evolution from 2013 of the mean (top) and the maximum (bottom) peak season O₃ concentrations at country level are shown in figure 30. In this way, the evolution along years of the average and maximum measured concentration levels can be seen for each country. Note that meteorological variability has a considerable impact on year-to-year changes in ambient air concentrations of air pollutants (EEA, 2020).

Figure 30: Evolution of mean (top) and maximum (bottom) peak season O₃ concentrations per country from 2013

Note: It is important to note that the figure is not based on a consistent set of stations. The number, location and classification of the stations included may vary from year to year.

5 Status of nitrogen dioxide ambient air concentrations

The reporting countries shown in Figure 1 submitted NO₂ data from 3557 stations for the annual limit value, 3142 stations for the hourly limit value, and 3152 stations for the daily WHO AQG level.

6 of the countries in EU-27 and 2 other reporting countries (Figure 31) recorded concentrations above the annual limit value (40 µg/m³). This happened in 2 % of all the stations measuring NO₂. On the contrary, 67 % of stations, located in 27 of the countries in EU-27 and 10 other reporting countries reported concentrations above the WHO AQG level of 10 µg/m³. Figure 31 shows the measured annual mean NO₂ concentrations.

66 % of all values above the annual limit value were observed at traffic stations. Furthermore, 100 % of the stations with concentrations above the annual limit value were located in urban or suburban areas.

Concentrations above the hourly limit value (200 µg/m³) were observed in 1.08 % (34 stations) of all reporting stations, mostly at urban traffic stations. They were observed in one countries. (Türkiye (thirty-four)).

Finally, concentrations above the daily NO₂ WHO AQG level (25 µg/m³) were registered in 72 % (2276 stations) of all the reporting stations in 27 of the countries in EU-27 and 10 other reporting countries (Figure 34).

Figure 31: Map and boxplot of NO₂ concentrations in 2024

Note: Observed concentrations of NO₂ in 2024. The last two colour categories correspond to values above the EU annual limit value (40 µg/m³), while the first colour category indicates stations reporting values below the WHO AQG level for NO₂ (10 µg/m³). Only stations with more than 75 % of valid data have been included in the map.

Note: The graph is based on the annual mean concentration values. For each country, the number of stations considered for 2024 (in brackets) are given. The boxplot represents the lowest (bottom of the whisker), highest (top of the whisker) and average (black dot) annual mean values (in µg/m³). The rectangles mark the 25th and 75th percentiles. At 25 % of the stations, levels are below the 25th percentile; at 25 % of the stations, concentrations are above the 75th percentile. The limit value set by EU legislation is marked by the horizontal line. The WHO AQG level is marked by the lower dashed horizontal line. The graph should be read in relation to the above map, as a country's situation depends on the number of stations considered.

The highest value in the boxplot, Türkiye ($101 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$), has not been included in the graph for representation purposes.

Figure 32 shows the maps of the observed NO_2 annual mean concentrations for the last four years. In this way, any significant change in the spatial distribution of the values above the set thresholds in the legends can be observed. These maps are based on officially reported validated data (CDR).

Figure 32: Map of NO_2 concentrations (annual mean) for the last 4 years

Maps for years before 2023 are different to the ones published in previous reports because the bands in the legend have been modified to accommodate the 2030 EU annual limit value (EU, 2024).

Heatmaps with the evolution from 2000 of the mean (top) and the maximum (bottom) NO_2 annual mean concentrations at country level are shown in figure 33. In this way, the evolution along years of the average and maximum measured concentration levels can be seen for each country. Note that meteorological variability has a considerable impact on year-to-year changes in ambient air concentrations of air pollutants (EEA, 2020).

Figure 33: Evolution of mean (top) and maximum (bottom) NO₂ annual mean concentrations (annual limit value) per country from 2000

Note: It is important to note that the figure is not based on a consistent set of stations. The number, location and classification of the stations included may vary from year to year.

Figure 34: Map of NO₂ concentrations in 2024 - daily WHO AQG level

Note: Observed concentrations of NO₂ in 2024. The map shows the 99 percentile of the NO₂ daily mean concentrations, equivalent to 3–4 exceedance days per year, according to the definition of the daily WHO AQG level (25 µg/m³). The first colour category indicates stations with concentrations below this AQG level. Only stations with more than 75 % of valid data have been included in the map.

Figure 35 shows the maps of the 99 percentile of NO₂ daily mean concentrations (equivalent to the WHO AQG level for NO₂ daily mean level) for the last four years. In this way, any significant change in the spatial distribution of the values above the set thresholds in the legends can be observed. These maps are based on officially reported validated data (CDR).

Figure 35: Maps of NO₂ concentrations (daily WHO AQG level) for the last 4 years

Heatmaps with the evolution from 2013 of the mean (top) and the maximum (bottom) 99 percentile of NO₂ daily mean concentrations at country level are shown in figure 36. In this way, the evolution along years of the average and maximum measured concentration levels can be seen for each country. Note that meteorological variability has a considerable impact on year-to-year changes in ambient air concentrations of air pollutants (EEA, 2020).

Figure 36: Evolution of mean (top) and maximum (bottom) 99 percentile of NO₂ daily mean concentrations (daily WHO AQG level) per country from 2013

Note: It is important to note that the figure is not based on a consistent set of stations. The number, location and classification of the stations included may vary from year to year.

6 Status of benzo[a]pyrene ambient air concentrations

A total of 792 stations in the reporting countries shown in Figure 1 reported BaP data with sufficient data coverage.

12 countries measured concentrations above 1.0 ng/m^3 (Figure 37). These were measured at 20 % of the reported BaP measurement stations (Figure 37), mainly at urban (76 % of all stations with values above 1.0 ng/m^3) and suburban (19 %) stations.

Regarding the reference level, all reporting countries, except for Cyprus, Luxembourg, Malta and Sweden have at least one station with concentrations above 0.12 ng/m^3 . Only 25 % of the reported stations had annual concentrations below the reference level.

Figure 37: Map and boxplot of BaP concentrations in 2024

Note: Observed concentrations of BaP in 2024. The first colour category correspond to concentrations under the estimated reference RL (0.12 ng/m³). The last colour category correspond to concentrations exceeding the 2004 Ambient Air Quality Directive target value of 1 ng/m³. Only stations reporting more than 13 % of valid data, as daily, weekly or monthly measurements, have been included in the map.

BaP concentrations in relation to the annual limit value in 2024 and number of stations considered for each country

Note: The graph is based on the annual mean concentration values. For each country, the number of stations considered for 2024 (in brackets) are given. The boxplot represents the lowest (bottom of the whisker), highest (top of the whisker) and average (black dot) annual mean values (in ng/m³). The rectangles mark the 25th and 75th percentiles. At 25 % of the stations, levels are below the 25th percentile; at 25 % of the stations, concentrations are above the 75th percentile. The upper horizontal line marks the concentration of 1.0 ng/m³. The lower horizontal line marks the estimated air quality RL. The graph should be read in relation to the above map, as a country's situation depends on the number of stations considered.

Figure 38 shows the maps of the observed BaP annual mean concentrations for the last four years. In this way, any significant change in the spatial distribution of the values above the

set thresholds in the legends can be observed. These maps are based on officially reported validated data (CDR).

Figure 38: Maps of BaP concentrations (annual mean) for the last 4 years

Heatmaps with the evolution from 2005 of the mean (top) and the maximum (bottom) BaP annual mean concentrations at country level are shown in figure 39. In this way, the evolution along years of the average and maximum measured concentration levels can be seen for each country. Note that meteorological variability has a considerable impact on year-to-year changes in ambient air concentrations of air pollutants (EEA, 2020).

Figure 39: Evolution of mean (top) and maximum (bottom) BaP annual mean concentrations (target value) per country from 2005

Note: It is important to note that the figure is not based on a consistent set of stations. The number, location and classification of the stations included may vary from year to year.

7 Status of sulphur dioxide, carbon monoxide, benzene and toxic metals ambient air concentrations

7.1 Sulphur dioxide

The reporting countries shown in Figure 1 reported measurements of SO₂ from 1500 stations for the hourly limit value and 1512 stations for the daily limit value.

14 stations ⁽⁷⁾ registered concentrations above the hourly limit value (350 µg/m³); and 16 stations ⁽⁸⁾ registered concentrations above the daily limit of 125 µg/m³ for SO₂ (Figure 40).

On the contrary, 71 (5 %) of all the stations reporting SO₂ levels, located in 12 reporting countries ⁽⁹⁾, measured SO₂ concentrations above the WHO AQG level of 40 µg/m³ for daily mean concentrations ⁽¹⁰⁾.

⁷Bosnia and Herzegovina (ten), Türkiye (three) and Iceland (one)

⁸Bosnia and Herzegovina (eleven), Türkiye (four) and Iceland (one).

⁹All reporting countries except Andorra, Austria, Belgium, Croatia, Cyprus, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, Greece, Hungary, Italy, Kosovo, Latvia, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Malta, Netherlands, North Macedonia, Norway, Portugal, Romania, Slovakia, Slovenia, Sweden and Switzerland.

¹⁰Although the WHO AQG level for daily means refers to the percentile 99 (3-4 exceedance days), here we have used the percentile 99.18 (3 exceedance days), so the daily WHO AQG level can be directly compared with the EU daily LV.

Figure 40: Map of SO₂ daily concentrations in 2024

Note: Observed concentrations of SO₂ in 2024. The map shows the percentile 99.18 of SO₂ daily means, indicating 3 exceedance days. It relates to the EU daily limit value (125 µg/m³) and to the WHO daily AQG level (40 µg/m³). Only stations with more than 75 % of valid data have been included in the map.

Figure 41 shows the maps of the observed SO₂ daily mean concentrations for the last four years. In this way, any significant change in the spatial distribution of the values above the set thresholds in the legends can be observed. These maps are based on officially reported validated data (CDR).

Figure 41: Maps of SO₂ concentrations (daily mean) for the last 4 years

Heatmaps with the evolution from 2000 of the mean (top) and the maximum (bottom) SO₂ daily mean concentrations at country level are shown in figure 42. In this way, the evolution along years of the average and maximum measured concentration levels can be seen for each country. Note that meteorological variability has a considerable impact on year-to-year changes in ambient air concentrations of air pollutants (EEA, 2020).

Figure 42: Evolution of mean (top) and maximum (bottom) SO₂ 99.18 percentile of daily mean concentrations (EU LV (125 µg/m³) and WHO AQG level (40 µg/m³)) per country from 2000

Note: It is important to note that the figure is not based on a consistent set of stations. The number, location and classification of the stations included may vary from year to year.

7.2 Carbon monoxide

All reporting countries shown in Figure 1 measured CO data from 920 operational stations for the daily limit value and from 929 stations for the daily WHO AQG level. Only 1 station (Figure 43) registered concentrations above the CO limit daily value (10 mg/m^3) and the WHO AQG level for the maximum daily 8-hour mean. This station was located in Germany (one).

3 stations registered concentrations above the daily WHO AQG level (4 mg/m^3). They were located in Türkiye (three) (Figure 45).

Figure 43: Map of CO concentrations in 2024

Note: Observed concentrations of CO in 2024. The map shows the CO maximum daily 8-hour mean. The last two colour categories correspond to values above the EU annual limit value and the WHO AQG (10 mg/m^3). Only stations with more than 75 % of valid data have been included in the map.

When concentrations are below the 'lower assessment threshold' (LAT), air quality can be assessed by means of only modelling or objective estimates. At 897 stations (98 % of locations), maximum daily 8-hour mean concentrations of CO were below the LAT of 5 mg/m^3 (first two colour categories in Figure 43).

Heatmaps with the evolution from 2000 of the mean (top) and the maximum (bottom) CO maximum daily 8-hour mean concentrations at country level are shown in Figure 44. In this way, the evolution along years of the average and maximum measured concentration levels can be seen for each country. Note that meteorological variability has a considerable impact on year-to-year changes in ambient air concentrations of air pollutants (EEA, [2020](#)).

Figure 44: Evolution of mean (top) and maximum (bottom) CO maximum daily 8-hour mean concentrations (limit value) per country from 2000

Note: It is important to note that the figure is not based on a consistent set of stations. The number, location and classification of the stations included may vary from year to year.

Figure 45: Map of daily CO concentrations in 2024

Note: Observed concentrations of CO in 2024. The map shows the 99 percentile of CO daily concentrations, meaning 3–4 exceedance days. The first colour category corresponds to values below the WHO AQG level (4 mg/m³). Only stations with more than 75 % of valid data have been included in the map.

Figure 46 shows the maps of the 99 percentile of CO daily mean concentrations (equivalent to the WHO AQG for CO daily mean level) for the last four years. In this way, any significant change in the spatial distribution of the values above the set thresholds in the legends can be observed. These maps are based on officially reported validated data (CDR).

Figure 46: Maps of CO concentrations (daily WHO AQG level) for the last 4 years

Heatmaps with the evolution from 2013 of the mean (top) and the maximum (bottom) 99 percentile of CO daily mean concentrations at country level are shown in figure 47. In this way, the evolution along years of the average and maximum measured concentration levels can be seen for each country. Note that meteorological variability has a considerable impact on year-to-year changes in ambient air concentrations of air pollutants (EEA, 2020).

Figure 47: Evolution of mean (top) and maximum (bottom) 99 percentile of CO daily mean concentrations (daily WHO AQG level) per country from 2013

Note: It is important to note that the figure is not based on a consistent set of stations. The number, location and classification of the stations included may vary from year to year.

7.3 Benzene

C₆H₆ measurements were reported from a total of 786 stations in the reporting countries shown in Figure 1.

Concentrations above the limit value for C₆H₆ (5 µg/m³) were not observed at any stations. At 97 % of locations, annual mean concentrations of C₆H₆ were below the LAT of 2 µg/m³ (first two colour categories in Figure 48).

Regarding the estimated WHO reference level (1.7 µg/m³), 5 % of all stations reported concentrations above this reference level, distributed across 14 European countries ⁽¹¹⁾ (Figure 48).

Figure 48: Map of C₆H₆ concentrations in 2024

Note: Observed concentrations of C₆H₆ in 2024. The last colour category correspond to concentrations above the limit value of 5 µg/m³. The first colour category correspond to concentrations under the estimated WHO RL (1.7 µg/m³). Only stations reporting more than 50 % of valid data have been included in the map.

¹¹Albania, Belgium, Bulgaria, Croatia, Czechia, France, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Italy, Poland, Romania, Slovakia and Spain

Heatmaps with the evolution from 2000 of the mean (top) and the maximum (bottom) C₆H₆ annual mean concentrations at country level are shown in Figure 49. In this way, the evolution along years of the average and maximum measured concentration levels can be seen for each country. Note that meteorological variability has a considerable impact on year-to-year changes in ambient air concentrations of air pollutants (EEA, [2020](#)).

Figure 49: Evolution of mean (top) and maximum (bottom) C₆H₆ annual mean concentrations (limit value) per country from 2000

Note: It is important to note that the figure is not based on a consistent set of stations. The number, location and classification of the stations included may vary from year to year.

7.4 Toxic metals

Data for **Arsenic (As)** were reported from 631 stations in the reporting countries shown in Figure 1. 5 stations measured concentrations above the target value (6 ng/m^3), located in: Belgium (two), Finland (one), Germany (one) and Spain (one), and 3 of these were industrial. Concentrations of As below the LAT (2.4 ng/m^3) were reported at 97 % of the stations (Figure 50).

Figure 50: Map of As concentrations in 2024

Note: Observed concentrations of As in 2024. The last two colour categories correspond to concentrations above the EU target value. Only stations reporting more than 13 % of valid data have been included in the map.

Heatmaps with the evolution from 2000 of the mean (top) and the maximum (bottom) As annual mean concentrations at country level are shown in Figure 51. In this way, the evolution along years of the average and maximum measured concentration levels can be seen for each country. Note that meteorological variability has a considerable impact on year-to-year changes in ambient air concentrations of air pollutants (EEA, [2020](#)).

Figure 51: Evolution of mean (top) and maximum (bottom) As annual mean concentrations (target value) per country from 2000

Note: It is important to note that the figure is not based on a consistent set of stations. The number, location and classification of the stations included may vary from year to year.

Cadmium (Cd) data were reported from 651 stations in the reporting countries shown in Figure 1. Concentrations above the target value (5 ng/m³) were not observed at any stations. At the great majority of stations (99 %), Cd concentrations were below the LAT (2 ng/m³) (Figure 52).

Figure 52: Map of Cd concentrations in 2024

Note: Observed concentrations of Cd in 2024. The last two colour categories correspond to concentrations above the target value. Only stations reporting more than 13 % of valid data have been included in the map.

Heatmaps with the evolution from 2000 of the mean (top) and the maximum (bottom) Cd annual mean concentrations at country level are shown in Figure 53. In this way, the evolution along years of the average and maximum measured concentration levels can be seen for each country. Note that meteorological variability has a considerable impact on year-to-year changes in ambient air concentrations of air pollutants (EEA, [2020](#)).

Figure 53: Evolution of mean (top) and maximum (bottom) Cd annual mean concentrations (target value) per country from 2000

Note: It is important to note that the figure is not based on a consistent set of stations. The number, location and classification of the stations included may vary from year to year.

Lead (Pb) data were reported from 636 stations in the reporting countries shown in Figure 1. Concentrations above the $0.5 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ limit value were observed at only 1 stations located in: Italy (one). 630 stations (99 % of the total) reported Pb concentrations below the LAT of $0.25 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$.

Figure 54: Map of Pb concentrations in 2024

Note: Observed concentrations of Pb in 2024. The last two colour categories correspond to concentrations above the EU annual limit value. Only stations reporting more than 13 % of valid data have been included in the map. Source: EEA, 2024.

Heatmaps with the evolution from 2000 of the mean (top) and the maximum (bottom) Pb annual mean concentrations at country level are shown in Figure 55. In this way, the evolution along years of the average and maximum measured concentration levels can be seen for each country. Note that meteorological variability has a considerable impact on year-to-year changes in ambient air concentrations of air pollutants (EEA, [2020](#)).

Figure 55: Evolution of mean (top) and maximum (bottom) Pb annual mean concentrations (limit value) per country from 2000

Note: It is important to note that the figure is not based on a consistent set of stations. The number, location and classification of the stations included may vary from year to year.

Nickel (Ni) data were reported from 633 stations in the reporting countries shown in Figure 1. Concentrations were above the target value of 20 ng/m³ at 4 stations in: Italy (two), Finland (one) and France (one), 4 of which were industrial. About 99 % of the stations reported Ni concentrations below the LAT of 10 ng/m³ (Figure 56).

Figure 56: Map of Ni concentrations in 2024

Note: Observed concentrations of Ni in 2024. The last two colour categories correspond to concentrations above the target value. Only stations reporting more than 13 % of valid data have been included in the map.

Heatmaps with the evolution from 2000 of the mean (top) and the maximum (bottom) Ni annual mean concentrations at country level are shown in Figure 57. In this way, the evolution along years of the average and maximum measured concentration levels can be seen for each country. Note that meteorological variability has a considerable impact on year-to-year changes in ambient air concentrations of air pollutants (EEA, 2020).

Figure 57: Evolution of mean (top) and maximum (bottom) Ni annual mean concentrations (target value) per country from 2000

Note: It is important to note that the figure is not based on a consistent set of stations. The number, location and classification of the stations included may vary from year to year.

8 Abbreviations, units and symbols

$\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$: microgram(s) per cubic metre

AAQD: Ambient Air Quality Directives

AEI: Average exposure indicator for PM_{2.5} concentrations

AQG: Air quality guideline

As: Arsenic

BaP: Benzo[a]pyrene

C₆H₆: Benzene

Cd: Cadmium

CDR: Central data repository

CO: Carbon monoxide

ECO: Exposure concentration obligation

EEA: European Environment Agency

ETC HE: European Topic Centre on Human health and the Environment

EU: European Union

LAT: Lower assessment threshold

LV: limit value

mg/m^3 : milligram(s) per cubic metre

NERT: National exposure reduction target

ng/m^3 : nanogram(s) per cubic metre

Ni: Nickel

NO₂: Nitrogen dioxide

O₃: Ozone

Pb: Lead

PM: Particulate matter

PM_{2.5}: Particulate matter with a diameter of 2.5 µm or less

PM₁₀: Particulate matter with a diameter of 10 µm or less

RL: Reference level

SO₂: Sulphur dioxide

TV: target value

WHO: World Health Organization

9 Annex 1

Data included in this report was received by 09 February 2026 from the reporting countries. By that date the number of stations by country aggregation reporting each pollutant is summarized in Table 3. Data from stations that do not fulfil the criteria from Box 1.1 are excluded from this report.

Table 3: Number of stations reporting 2024 data with the minimum data coverage for at least one of the aggregations used in the report, by 09 February 2026

Countries	PM10	PM2.5	O3	NO2	BaP	SO2	CO	C6H6	As	Cd	Pb	Ni
EU27	2958	2001	2029	3244	776	1242	744	770	615	632	619	617
EEA32	3304	2173	2204	3493	792	1482	872	781	629	649	634	631
Total	3365	2223	2262	3560	792	1549	930	786	631	651	636	633

Data not included in this report is summarized in Table 4:

Table 4: Reporting outliers of 2024 air quality data by 09 February 2026

Country	Station Eol Code	Pollutant	Aggregation(*)	Year	Value	Units	Data Coverage
Bosnia and Herzegovina	BA0039A	SO2	P1Y-day-max-per99.18	2024	570	ug/m3	90
Hungary	HU0032A	Pb	P1Y	2024	4	ug/m3	15
Hungary	HU0049A	Pb	P1Y	2024	3	ug/m3	14
Hungary	HU0044A	Pb	P1Y	2024	3	ug/m3	15
Hungary	HU0050A	Pb	P1Y	2024	2	ug/m3	15
Hungary	HU0027A	Pb	P1Y	2024	5	ug/m3	15
Hungary	HU0052A	Pb	P1Y	2024	2	ug/m3	15
Hungary	HU0022A	Pb	P1Y	2024	6	ug/m3	15
Hungary	HU0002R	Pb	P1Y	2024	3	ug/m3	15
Hungary	HU0046A	Pb	P1Y	2024	3	ug/m3	15
Hungary	HU0041A	Pb	P1Y	2024	3	ug/m3	15
Malta	MT00009	Pb	P1Y	2024	3	ug/m3	58

Table 4: Reporting outliers of 2024 air quality data by 09 February 2026 (continued)

Country	Station Eol Code	Pollutant	Aggregation(*)	Year	Value	Units	Data Coverage
Malta	MT00011	Pb	P1Y	2024	4	ug/m3	53
Türkiye	TR0049A	PM2.5	P1Y-P1D-per99	2024	324	ug/m3	89

(*) <https://dd.eionet.europa.eu/vocabulary/aq/aggregationprocess/view>

The following table (Table 5) summarizes the average exposure indicator (AEI) by country.

Table 5: AEI calculated at national level

Country	Reference years	Initial AEI	Percentage of reduction	NERT
Austria	2009-2011	17.8	15.00	15.1
Belgium	2009-2011	19.0	20.00	15.2
Bulgaria	2008-2010	36.0	50.00	18.0
Croatia	2013-2015	20.6	20.00	16.5
Cyprus	2009-2011	21.5	20.00	17.2
Czechia	2009-2011	26.6	32.30	18.0
Denmark	2008-2010	14.0	15.00	11.9
Estonia	2009-2011	5.9	0.00	8.5
Finland	2009-2011	8.3	0.00	8.5
France	2009-2011	17.3	15.00	14.7
Germany	2008-2010	16.0	15.00	13.6
Greece	2008-2010	17.0	15.00	14.5
Hungary	2009-2010	21.0	20.00	16.8
Iceland	2008-2010	10.8	10.00	9.7
Ireland	2009-2011	10.2	10.00	9.2
Italy	2009-2011	19.9	20.00	15.9
Latvia	2008-2010	18.0	20.00	14.4
Lithuania	2009-2011	12.3	10.00	11.1
Luxembourg	2009-2010	17.4	15.00	14.8
Malta	2009-2011	13.2	15.00	11.2
Netherlands	2009-2011	17.0	15.00	14.5
Norway	2009-2011	10.0	10.00	9.0
Poland	2009-2011	27.8	35.25	18.0
Portugal	2008-2010	9.7	10.00	8.7
Romania	2009-2011	18.4	20.00	14.7
Slovakia	2009-2011	24.4	26.20	18.0
Slovenia	2009-2011	21.7	20.00	17.4
Spain	2009-2011	14.1	15.00	12.0
Sweden	2009-2011	6.6	0.00	8.5

Table 6 summarizes the number of sampling points per country with air quality levels above specific air quality objectives summarized through out this report. Sampling points that do not fulfil the criteria from Box 1.1 are excluded.

Table 6: Number of sampling points above air quality levels/objectives per reporting country

Levels/Objectives	Albania	Andorra	Austria	Belgium	Bosnia and Herzegovina	Bulgaria	Croatia	Cyprus	Czechia	Denmark	Estonia	Finland	France	Germany	Greece	Hungary	Iceland	Ireland	Italy	Kosovo	Latvia	Lithuania	Luxembourg	Malta	Montenegro	Netherlands	North Macedonia	Norway	Poland	Portugal	Romania	Serbia	Slovakia	Slovenia	Spain	Sweden	Switzerland	Türkiye	
PM ₁₀ daily LV (50 µg/m ³)	0	0	0	0	14	2	4	1	0	0	0	0	2	0	10	0	0	0	99	0	0	0	0	2	1	0	10	1	10	0	10	15	3	0	41	3	0	189	
PM ₁₀ daily 2030 LV (45 µg/m ³)	0	0	4	0	18	24	6	3	24	0	1	2	15	0	26	7	0	0	265	5	2	2	0	4	1	0	11	14	123	5	38	16	13	10	114	14	0	226	
PM ₁₀ daily WHO AQG level (45 µg/m ³)	0	1	66	4	19	35	15	3	122	0	1	13	64	75	34	23	3	9	523	9	6	12	0	5	1	3	11	36	231	52	69	16	42	20	287	37	0	242	
PM ₁₀ annual LV (40 µg/m ³)	0	0	0	0	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	6	1	0	0	1	7	0	0	3	0	0	109	
PM ₁₀ annual WHO AQG level (15 µg/m ³)	0	0	59	34	19	38	12	3	103	1	1	3	98	73	37	22	0	6	508	7	7	10	2	5	1	31	11	20	237	43	75	16	46	20	311	24	0	244	
PM ₁₀ annual 2030 LV (20 µg/m ³)	0	0	9	1	16	29	7	2	38	0	0	0	27	8	32	11	0	0	353	1	2	5	0	4	1	1	11	5	172	12	50	16	24	9	169	5	0	236	
PM _{2.5} annual LV (25 µg/m ³)	0	0	0	0	6	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	6	0	0	0	1	5	0	0	0	0	0	5	
PM _{2.5} annual WHO AQG level (5 µg/m ³)	0	1	65	73	12	9	18	4	94	9	0	4	220	310	22	12	0	58	315	12	5	13	4	5	1	53	12	38	137	9	57	12	47	18	277	19	7	105	
PM _{2.5} daily WHO AQG level (15 µg/m ³)	0	1	65	81	12	9	18	4	95	9	2	11	227	318	22	12	1	61	317	12	5	11	4	5	1	53	12	43	137	14	57	12	47	18	288	22	8	105	
O ₃ max daily 8h mean TV (120 µg/m ³)	0	0	14	0	13	3	3	2	5	0	0	0	2	3	17	6	0	0	150	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	7	2	4	4	3	4	57	2	2	35	
O ₃ long-term objective (120 µg/m ³)	0	1	91	35	18	12	16	3	64	7	5	5	215	257	26	17	0	0	283	8	2	9	4	3	0	43	7	4	79	38	13	6	16	11	269	12	27	80	
O ₃ max daily 8h mean 2030 LTO (100 µg/m ³)	0	0	39	0	13	4	4	3	17	0	0	0	7	13	21	8	0	0	183	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	0	20	4	3	5	4	5	69	2	4	41	
O ₃ short-term WHO AQG level (100 µg/m ³)	0	1	107	35	20	13	16	3	64	8	9	15	265	273	29	17	0	0	317	8	6	13	5	3	0	44	9	10	86	45	19	6	20	11	369	18	30	90	
O ₃ peak season WHO AQG level (60 µg/m ³)	0	1	106	34	17	16	15	3	64	7	9	16	261	273	31	16	0	13	322	0	8	13	5	4	0	44	8	11	80	40	20	6	19	10	402	14	30	82	
O ₃ target value health (120 µg/m ³)	0	0	13	0	9	0	1	2	6	0	0	0	26	20	9	4	0	0	160	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	2	2	1	3	1	4	34	0	14	15	
O ₃ target value health 2030 (120 µg/m ³)	0	0	42	3	9	0	1	2	23	0	0	0	57	68	10	6	0	0	192	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	0	10	4	3	3	4	4	60	0	20	21	
O ₃ target value vegetation (18000 µg/m ³ ·h)	0	0	10	0	4	1	4	2	1	0	0	0	14	1	11	3	0	0	176	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	3	2	2	53	0	3	14		
NO ₂ annual LV (40 µg/m ³)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4	1	4	0	0	0	11	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	2	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	45	
NO ₂ annual WHO AQG level (10 µg/m ³)	0	1	104	111	16	20	11	2	58	4	1	11	189	442	25	15	2	22	452	7	4	9	102	4	4	57	14	34	91	38	23	12	23	7	273	32	23	146	
NO ₂ hourly LV (200 µg/m ³)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	34
NO ₂ hourly 2030 LV (200 µg/m ³)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	43
NO ₂ daily WHO AQG level (25 µg/m ³)	0	1	118	78	18	21	13	2	72	4	3	21	227	279	25	15	3	27	472	8	5	10	6	4	4	67	14	38	91	39	24	12	25	8	315	38	25	144	
NO ₂ daily 2030 LV (50 µg/m ³)	0	0	1	1	3	5	1	0	1	0	0	0	10	2	12	1	0	4	67	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	2	6	4	3	7	2	0	1	19	0	0	103	
BaP annual LV (1 ng/m ³)	0	0	2	0	0	2	3	0	17	0	0	2	1	0	0	2	0	0	12	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	108	0	0	0	9	1	0	0	0	0	
BaP annual WHO AQG level (0.12 ng/m ³)	0	0	31	2	0	11	6	0	58	1	4	6	15	52	3	16	0	2	127	0	3	4	0	0	0	1	0	4	169	0	10	0	21	5	35	0	5	0	

Table 6: Number of sampling points above air quality levels/objectives per reporting country (continued)

Levels/Objectives	Albania	Andorra	Austria	Belgium	Bosnia and Herzegovina	Bulgaria	Croatia	Cyprus	Czechia	Denmark	Estonia	Finland	France	Germany	Greece	Hungary	Iceland	Ireland	Italy	Kosovo	Latvia	Lithuania	Luxembourg	Malta	Montenegro	Netherlands	North Macedonia	Norway	Poland	Portugal	Romania	Serbia	Slovakia	Slovenia	Spain	Sweden	Switzerland	Türkiye		
SO ₂ hourly LV (350 µg/m ³)	0	0	0	0	10	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	
SO ₂ hourly LV 2030 (350 µg/m ³)	0	0	1	0	14	3	0	0	4	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	4	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	6
SO ₂ daily LV (125 µg/m ³)	0	0	0	0	12	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4	
SO ₂ daily WHO AQG level (40 µg/m ³)	0	0	0	0	17	4	0	0	4	0	0	0	1	3	0	0	5	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	2	0	0	2	0	0	5	0	0	0	26	
CO daily LV (10 mg/m ³)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		
CO daily WHO AQG level (4 mg/m ³)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3		
C ₆ H ₆ annual WHO RL (1.7 µg/m ³)	1	0	0	6	0	1	1	0	4	0	0	0	1	2	5	1	0	0	14	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	1	0	1	0	2	0	0	0		
C ₆ H ₆ annual 2030 LV (3.4 µg/m ³)	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		
As annual TV (6 ng/m ³)	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0		
As annual LAT (2.4 ng/m ³)	0	0	0	5	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	2	0	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	6	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0			
Cd annual LAT (2 ng/m ³)	0	0	0	3	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0		
Pb annual LV (0.5 µg/m ³)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		
Pb annual LAT (0.25 µg/m ³)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	5	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0		
Ni annual TV (20 ng/m ³)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		
Ni annual LAT (10 ng/m ³)	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	2	0	0	0	0	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0			

10 Annex 2 - Air quality status in relation to the new standards in the revised AAQD (EU) 2024/2081

On 20 November 2024, the revised Directive (EU) 2024/2881 (EU, 2024) on ambient air quality and cleaner air for Europe was published and it entered into force on 10 December 2024. This Directive amends and recasts Directives 2004/107/EC (EU, 2004) and 2008/50/EC (EU, 2008). Among other changes, it has introduced new air quality (AQ) standards (or revised the ones in the 2004 and 2008 Directives) setting the attainment date at 1 January 2030. The revised and new standards for the protection of human health are summarised in table 7).

Table 7: Air quality standards for the protection of health, as given in the revised EU Ambient Air Quality Directive (EU) 2024/2881

Pollutant	Averaging period	Legal nature and concentration	Comments
PM ₁₀	1 day	Limit value: 45 µg/m ³	Not to be exceeded more than 18 times per calendar year
		Alert threshold: 90 µg/m ³	To be measured as a daily average over 3 consecutive days or less at locations representative of air quality over at least 100 km ² or an entire zone, whichever is the smaller
		Information threshold: 90 µg/m ³	To be measured over 1 day at locations representative of air quality over at least 100 km ² or an entire zone, whichever is the smaller
	Calendar year	Limit value: 20 µg/m ³	
PM _{2,5}	1 day	Limit value: 25 µg/m ³	Not to be exceeded more than 18 times per calendar year
		Alert threshold: 50 µg/m ³	To be measured as a daily average over 3 consecutive days or less at locations representative of air quality over at least 100 km ² or an entire zone, whichever is the smaller
		Information threshold: 50 µg/m ³	To be measured over 1 day at locations representative of air quality over at least 100 km ² or an entire zone, whichever is the smaller
	Calendar year	Limit value: 10 µg/m ³	
		Average exposure reduction obligation, 10-25% reduction of the Average Exposure Indicator (AEI) in 2020	The percentage reduction depends on the initial AEI in 2020 ^(a)
		Average exposure concentration objective, AIE: 5 µg/m ³	
O ₃	1 hour	Alert threshold: 240 µg/m ³	
		Information threshold: 180 µg/m ³	
	Maximum daily 8-hour mean ^(b)	Target value: 120 µg/m ³	Not to be exceeded on more than 18 days per calendar year averaged over 3 years ^(c)

Table 7: Air quality standards for the protection of health, as given in the revised EU Ambient Air Quality Directive (EU) 2024/2881 (continued)

Pollutant	Averaging period	Legal nature and concentration	Comments
NO ₂	Maximum daily 8-hour mean within a calendar year	Long term objective: 100 µg/m ³	Not to be exceeded more than 3 days per calendar year (99th percentile)
	1 hour	Limit value: 200 µg/m ³	Not to be exceeded more than 3 times per calendar year
		Alert threshold: 200 µg/m ³	To be measured as a daily average over 3 consecutive days or less at locations representative of air quality over at least 100 km ² or an entire zone, whichever is the smaller
		Information threshold: 150 µg/m ³	To be measured over 1 day at locations representative of air quality over at least 100 km ² or an entire zone, whichever is the smaller
	1 day	Limit value: 50 µg/m ³	Not to be exceeded more than 18 times per calendar year
	Calendar year	Limit value: 20 µg/m ³	
		Average exposure reduction obligation, 15-25% reduction of the Average Exposure Indicator (AEI) in 2020	The percentage reduction depends on the initial AEI in 2020 ^(a)
Average exposure concentration objective, AIE: 10 µg/m ³			
BaP	Calendar year	Limit value: 1,0 ng/m ³	
SO ₂	1 hour	Limit value: 350 µg/m ³	Not to be exceeded more than 3 times per calendar year
		Alert threshold: 350 µg/m ³	To be measured as a daily average over 3 consecutive days or less at locations representative of air quality over at least 100 km ² or an entire zone, whichever is the smaller
		Information threshold: 275 µg/m ³	To be measured over 1 day at locations representative of air quality over at least 100 km ² or an entire zone, whichever is the smaller
	1 day	Limit value: 50 µg/m ³	Not to be exceeded more than 18 times per calendar year
	CO	Maximum daily 8-hour mean ^(b)	Limit value: 10 mg/m ³
1 day		Limit value: 4 mg/m ³	Not to be exceeded more than 18 times per calendar year
C ₆ H ₆	Calendar year	Limit value: 3.4 µg/m ³	
Pb	Calendar year	Limit value: 0.5 µg/m ³	
As	Calendar year	Limit value: 6,0 ng/m ³	
Cd	Calendar year	Limit value: 5,0 ng/m ³	
Ni	Calendar year	Limit value: 20 ng/m ³	

Table 7: Air quality standards for the protection of health, as given in the revised EU Ambient Air Quality Directive (EU) 2024/2881 (continued)

Pollutant	Averaging period	Legal nature and concentration	Comments
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Notes:

^a AEI: based upon measurements at all sampling points in urban background locations in average exposure territorial units throughout the territory of a Member State, assessed as a 3-year running annual mean.

^b The maximum daily 8-hour mean concentration shall be selected by examining 8-hour running averages, calculated from hourly data and updated each hour. Each 8-hour average so calculated shall be assigned to the day on which it ends, i.e. the first calculation period for any 1 day shall be the period from 17:00 on the previous day to 1:00 on that day; the last calculation period for any 1 day shall be the period from 16:00 to 24:00 on that day.

^c If the 3-year average cannot be determined on the basis of a full and consecutive set of annual data, the minimum annual data required for checking compliance with the ozone target value shall be valid data for 1 year.

This annex analyses the situation in year 2024 with respect to some of the new and/or revised AQ standards ⁽¹²⁾ using the same air quality data as those in the main section. It provides:

- a European overview of the 2024 monitoring stations reported, and of their concentrations in relation to some EU legal standards defined in the Directive (EU) 2024/2881 (EU, 2024);
- a map with the 2024 concentrations at station level for each pollutant relevant to each AQ standard;
- a boxplot graph summarizing for each country the range of concentrations (highlighting the lowest, highest, average and the 25 and 75 percentiles) for PM₁₀, PM_{2.5}, O₃, NO₂ and SO₂.

It should be noted that this assessment is only intended to shed light on the current situation in relation to the 2030 AQ standards, and the ‘distance to target’, i.e. the scale of the challenge to meet those standards by 2030. This analysis may also help to identify air quality zones where air quality roadmaps may need to be established. Roadmaps are air quality plans that must be implemented where, from 2026 to 2029, levels of pollutants are foreseen to be above the 2030 limit and target values.

¹²Only for the limit values and O3 target value and long-term objective

10.1 Status of PM₁₀ concentrations

Twenty-one countries in EU-27, and seven other reporting countries reported PM₁₀ concentrations above the 2030 EU daily limit value of 45 µg/m³, more than 18 days over the calendar year (Figure 58). This applied to 30 % (993) of reporting stations.

Concentrations above the 2030 PM₁₀ annual limit value (20 µg/m³) were monitored in 37 % (1256 stations) of all the reporting stations, located in 22 countries in EU-27, and 7 other reporting countries (Figure 59).

Figure 58: Map and boxplot of PM₁₀ concentrations in 2024 - 2030 daily limit value

Note: The figure shows observed concentrations of PM₁₀ in 2024. The possibility of subtracting contributions to the measured concentrations from natural sources and winter road sanding/salting has not been considered. The map shows the 95.07 percentile of the PM₁₀ daily mean concentrations, representing the 19th highest value in a complete series. It is related to the 2030 PM₁₀ daily limit value, allowing 18 exceedances of the 45 µg/m³ threshold over 1 year. The last two colour categories indicate stations with concentrations above this daily limit value. Only stations with more than 75 % of valid data, and more than 13 % in the case of fixed random measurements, have been included in the map.

Note: The graph is based on the 95.07 percentile of daily mean concentration values corresponding to the 19th highest daily mean in complete time series. For each country, the number of stations considered for 2024 (in brackets) are given. The boxplot represents the lowest (bottom of the whisker), highest (top of the whisker) and average (black dot) 95.07 percentile values (in µg/m³). The rectangles mark the 25th and 75th percentiles. At 25% of the stations, levels are below the 25th percentile; at 25 % of the stations, concentrations are above the 75th percentile. The daily limit value set by EU legislation for 2030 is marked by the horizontal line. The graph should be read in relation to the above map, as a country's situation depends on the number of stations considered.

Figure 59: Map and Boxplot of PM₁₀ concentrations in 2024 - 2030 annual limit value

Note: Observed concentrations of PM₁₀ in 2024. The possibility of subtracting contributions to the measured concentrations from natural sources and winter road sanding/salting has not been considered. The last three colour categories indicate stations reporting concentrations above the 2030 EU annual limit value (20 µg/m³). Only stations with more than 75 % of valid data, and more than 13 % in the case of fixed random measurements, have been included in the map.

Note: The graph is based on annual mean concentration values. For each country, the number of stations considered for 2024 (in brackets) are given. The boxplot represents the lowest (bottom of the whisker), highest (top of the whisker) and average (black dot) annual mean values (in µg/m³). The rectangles mark the 25th and 75th percentiles. At 25 % of the stations, levels are below the 25th percentile; at 25 % of the stations, concentrations are above the 75th percentile. The annual limit value set by EU legislation for 2030 is marked by the continuous horizontal line. The graph should be read in relation to the above map, as a country's situation depends on the number of stations considered.

10.2 Status of PM_{2.5} concentrations

Seventeen countries in EU-27, and six other reporting countries reported PM_{2.5} concentrations above the 2030 EU daily limit value of 25 µg/m³, more than 18 days over the calendar year (Figure 60). This was the case for 33 % (729) of reporting stations (Figure 60).

The PM_{2.5} concentrations were higher than the 2030 EU annual limit value (10 µg/m³) in twenty-one countries in EU-27 and six other reporting countries (Figure 61). These concentrations above the limit value were registered in 39 % (874 stations) of all the reporting stations.

Figure 60: Map and boxplot of PM_{2.5} concentrations in 2024 - 2030 daily limit value

Note: The figure shows observed concentrations of PM_{2.5} in 2024. The possibility of subtracting contributions to the measured concentrations from natural sources has not been considered. The map shows the 95.07 percentile of the PM_{2.5} daily mean concentrations, representing the 19th highest value in a complete series. It is related to the 2030 PM_{2.5} daily limit value, allowing 18 exceedances of the 25 µg/m³ threshold over 1 year. The last two colour categories indicate stations with concentrations above this daily limit value. Only stations with more than 75 % of valid data, and more than 13 % in the case of fixed random measurements, have been included in the map.

Note: The graph is based on the 95.07 percentile of daily mean concentration values corresponding to the 19th highest daily mean in complete time series. For each country, the number of stations considered for 2024 (in brackets) are given. The boxplot represents the lowest (bottom of the whisker), highest (top of the whisker) and average (black dot) 95.07 percentile values (in µg/m³). The rectangles mark the 25th and 75th percentiles. At 25% of the stations, levels are below the 25th percentile; at 25 % of the stations, concentrations are above the 75th percentile. The daily limit value set by EU legislation for 2030 is marked by the horizontal line. The graph should be read in relation to the above map, as a country's situation depends on the number of stations considered.

Figure 61: Map and Boxplot of PM_{2.5} concentrations in 2024 - 2030 annual limit value

Note: Observed concentrations of PM_{2.5} in 2024. The possibility of subtracting contributions to the measured concentrations from natural sources has not been considered. The last three colour categories indicate stations reporting concentrations above the 2030 EU annual limit value (10 µg/m³). Only stations with more than 75 % of valid data, and more than 13 % in the case of fixed random measurements, have been included in the map.

PM_{2.5} concentrations in 2024 in relation to the 2030 standard annual limit value and number of stations considered for each country

Note: The graph is based on annual mean concentration values. For each country, the number of stations considered for 2024 (in brackets) are given. The boxplot represents the lowest (bottom of the whisker), highest (top of the whisker) and average (black dot) annual mean values (in µg/m³). The rectangles mark the 25th and 75th percentiles. At 25 % of the stations, levels are below the 25th percentile; at 25 % of the stations, concentrations are above the 75th percentile. The annual limit value set by EU legislation for 2030 is marked by the continuous horizontal line. The graph should be read in relation to the above map, as a country's situation depends on the number of stations considered.

10.3 Status of O₃ ambient air concentrations

17 countries in EU-27 and 6 other reporting countries reported concentrations above the 2030 O₃ target value threshold (120 µg/m³) more than 18 times this year (Figure 62). In total, 22 % (474 stations) of all stations reporting O₃ showed concentrations above the 2030 target value threshold for the protection of human health. Furthermore, the 2022-2024 average of the annual number of days with maximum daily 8-hour means above 120 µg/m³ was higher than 18 (that is, above the 2030 target value) in 545 stations (28% of the total) in 18 countries of the EU-27 and 5 other reporting countries (Figure 63).

Since the 2030 long-term objective aligns with the short-term WHO AQG (100 µg/m³ as percentile 99), please refer to the main text and Figure 25 for an overview of the current situation in relation to the 2030 long-term objective.

Figure 62: Map and boxplot of O₃ concentrations in 2024 - 2030 target value threshold.

Note: Observed concentrations of O₃ in 2024. The map shows the 95.07 percentile of the O₃ maximum daily 8-hour mean, representing the 19th highest value in a complete series. It is related to the 2030 O₃ target value. At sites marked with the last two colour categories, the 19th highest daily O₃ concentrations were above the 120 µg/m³ threshold, implying values above the 2030 target value threshold. Please note that the legal definition of the target value considers not only 1 year but the average over 3 years.

Note: The graph is based, for each country, on the 95.07 percentile of the maximum daily 8-hour mean concentration values, corresponding to the 19th highest daily maximum of the running 8-hour mean in a complete time series. For each country, the number of stations considered for 2024 (in brackets) are given. The boxplot represents the lowest (bottom of the whisker), highest (top of the whisker) and average (black dot) values (in ..g/m³). The rectangles mark the 25th and 75th percentiles. At 25% of the stations, levels are below the 25th percentile; at 25% of the stations, concentrations are above the 75th percentile. The target value threshold set for 2030 by the EU legislation is marked by the horizontal line. Please note that the legal definition of the target value considers not only 1 year but the average over 3 years. The graph should be read in relation to the above map, as a country's situation depends on the number of stations considered.

Figure 63: Map and boxplot of O₃ concentrations in 2024 - 2030 target value human health

Note: The map shows the 2022–2024 average of the annual number of days with maximum daily 8–hour means above 120 µg/m³. The last three categories of the legend indicate stations with this average about 18, meaning above the O₃ target value 2030 for the protection of human health

Note: The graph is based, for each country, on the 2022–2024 average of the annual number of days with maximum daily 8–hour means above 120 µg/m³. For each country, the number of stations considered for the three years (in brackets) are given. The boxplot represents the lowest (bottom of the whisker), highest (top of the whisker) and average (black dot) values (in number of days). The rectangles mark the 25th and 75th percentiles. At 25% of the stations, the three–years average number of days are below the 25th percentile; at 25% of the stations, the three–years average number of days are above the 75th percentile. The 2030 target value set by the EU legislation is marked by the dashed horizontal line. The graph should be read in relation to the above map, as a country’s situation depends on the number of stations considered.

10.4 Status of NO₂ ambient air concentrations

24 of the countries in EU-27 and 7 other reporting countries (Figure 64) recorded concentrations above the 2030 EU annual limit value (20 µg/m³). This happened in 27 % (962 stations) of all the stations measuring NO₂.

72 % (692 stations) of all values above the 2030 EU annual limit value were observed at traffic stations.

Concentrations above the 2030 EU NO₂ daily limit value (50 µg/m³, not to be exceeded more than 18 days per year) were reported in 8 % (256 stations) of all the reporting stations in 17 of the countries in EU-27 and 5 other reporting countries (Figure 65).

Finally, concentrations above the hourly limit value (200 µg/m³, not to be exceeded more than 3 hours per year) were observed in 1.5 % (48 stations) of all reporting stations, mostly at urban traffic stations. They were observed in five countries (number stations): Türkiye (forty-three), Latvia (two), Germany (one), Italy (one) and Spain (one).

Figure 64: Map and Boxplot of NO₂ concentrations in 2024 - 2030 annual limit value

Note: Observed concentrations of NO₂ in 2024. The last three colour categories indicate stations reporting concentrations above the 2030 EU annual limit value (20 µg/m³). Only stations with more than 75 % of valid data have been included in the map.

Note: The graph is based on annual mean concentration values. For each country, the number of stations considered for 2024 (in brackets) are given. The boxplot represents the lowest (bottom of the whisker), highest (top of the whisker) and average (black dot) annual mean values (in µg/m³). The rectangles mark the 25th and 75th percentiles. At 25 % of the stations, levels are below the 25th percentile; at 25 % of the stations, concentrations are above the 75th percentile. The annual limit value set by EU legislation for 2030 is marked by the continuous horizontal line. The graph should be read in relation to the above map, as a country's situation depends on the number of stations considered.

Figure 65: Map and boxplot of NO₂ concentrations in 2024 - 2030 daily limit value

Note: The figure shows observed concentrations of NO₂ in 2024. The map shows the 95.07 percentile of the NO₂ daily mean concentrations, representing the 19th highest value in a complete series. It is related to the 2030 NO₂ daily limit value, allowing 18 exceedances of the 50 µg/m³ threshold over 1 year. The last two colour categories indicate stations with concentrations above this daily limit value. Only stations with more than 75 % of valid data have been included in the map.

Note: The graph is based on the 95.07 percentile of daily mean concentration values corresponding to the 19th highest daily mean in complete time series. For each country, the number of stations considered for 2024 (in brackets) are given. The boxplot represents the lowest (bottom of the whisker), highest (top of the whisker) and average (black dot) 95.07 percentile values (in µg/m³). The rectangles mark the 25th and 75th percentiles. At 25% of the stations, levels are below the 25th percentile; at 25 % of the stations, concentrations are above the 75th percentile. The daily limit value set by EU legislation for 2030 is marked by the horizontal line. The graph should be read in relation to the above map, as a country's situation depends on the number of stations considered.

10.5 Status of SO₂ concentrations

1 of the country and 3 other reporting countries (Figure 66) recorded concentrations above the 2030 EU annual limit value (20 µg/m³). This happened in 1.3 % of all the stations measuring SO₂.

Concentrations above the 2030 EU SO₂ daily limit value (50 µg/m³, not to be exceeded more than 18 days per year) were registered in 2 % (24 stations) of all the reporting stations in 2 of the countries in EU-27 and 3 other reporting countries (Figure 67).

Finally, concentrations above the hourly limit value (350 µg/m³ not to be exceeded in more than 3 occasions) were observed in 2.5 % (38 stations) of all reporting stations. They were observed in twelve countries (number stations): Bosnia and Herzegovina (fourteen), Türkiye (six), Czechia (four), Iceland (four), Bulgaria (three), Austria (one), France (one), Germany (one), Italy (one), Montenegro (one), Poland (one) and Serbia (one).

Figure 66: Map and Boxplot of SO₂ concentrations in 2024 - 2030 annual limit value

Note: Observed concentrations of SO₂ in 2024. The last two colour categories indicate stations reporting concentrations above the 2030 EU annual limit value (20 µg/m³). Only stations with more than 75 % of valid data have been included in the map.

Note: The graph is based on annual mean concentration values. For each country, the number of stations considered for 2024 (in brackets) are given. The boxplot represents the lowest (bottom of the whisker), highest (top of the whisker) and average (black dot) annual mean values (in µg/m³). The rectangles mark the 25th and 75th percentiles. At 25 % of the stations, levels are below the 25th percentile; at 25 % of the stations, concentrations are above the 75th percentile. The annual limit value set by EU legislation for 2030 is marked by the continuous horizontal line. The graph should be read in relation to the above map, as a country's situation depends on the number of stations considered.

Figure 67: Map and boxplot of SO₂ concentrations in 2024 - 2030 daily limit value

Note: The figure shows observed concentrations of SO₂ in 2024. The map shows the 95.07 percentile of the SO₂ daily mean concentrations, representing the 19th highest value in a complete series. It is related to the 2030 SO₂ daily limit value, allowing 18 exceedances of the 50 µg/m³ threshold over 1 year. The last two colour categories indicate stations with concentrations above this daily limit value. Only stations with more than 75 % of valid data have been included in the map.

Note: The graph is based on the 95.07 percentile of daily mean concentration values corresponding to the 19th highest daily mean in complete series. For each country, the number of stations considered for 2024 (in brackets) are given. The boxplot represents the lowest (bottom of the whisker) and highest (top of the whisker) and average (black dot) 95.07 percentile values (in µg/m³). The rectangles mark the 25th and 75th percentiles. At 25% of the stations, levels are below the 25th percentile; at 25 % of the stations, concentrations are above the 75th percentile. The daily limit value set by EU legislation for 2030 is marked by the horizontal line. The graph should be read in relation to the above map, as a country's situation depends on the number of stations considered.

10.6 Status of CO concentrations

The 2030 EU maximum daily 8-hour mean limit value is the same as the current one and therefore the situation has already been described in chapter 7.2.

None of the countries in EU-27 and no other reporting countries reported concentrations above de 2030 EU daily limit value (4 mg/m^3) (Figure 68).

Figure 68: Map of CO concentrations in 2024 - 2030 daily limit value

Note: Observed concentrations of CO in 2023. The map shows the 95.07 percentile of the CO daily mean concentrations, representing the 19th highest value in a complete series. It is related to the 2030 CO daily limit value, allowing 18 exceedances of the 4 mg/m^3 threshold over 1 year. The last two colour categories indicate stations with concentrations above this daily limit value. Only stations with more than 75 % of valid data have been included in the map.

10.7 Status of C₆H₆ concentrations

3 of the countries in EU-27 and none other reporting countries (Figure 69) recorded concentrations above the 2030 EU annual limit value (3,4 µg/m³). This happened in 0.8 % of all the stations measuring C₆H₆.

Figure 69: Map of C₆H₆ concentrations in 2024 - 2030 annual limit value

Note: Observed concentrations of C₆H₆ in 2023. The last two colour categories correspond to values above the 2030 EU annual limit value. Only stations with more than 75 % of valid data have been included in the map.

10.8 Status of other pollutants concentrations

For BaP, the 2030 EU annual limit value is 1,0 ng/m³. Please see the analysis against that value at chapter 6.

The 2030 EU annual limit value for Pb remains unchanged from the value currently in force under Directive 2008/50/EC. Therefore, please refer to chapter 7 for this analysis.

Similarly, for As, Cd and Ni, the 2030 EU limit values are the same as the current target values. Therefore, please refer to chapter 7 for this analysis.

References

- EEA (2020). Air quality in Europe–2020 report. *EEA Report No 9/2020*, <https://www.eea.europa.eu/en/analysis/publications/air-quality-in-europe-2020-report>.
- EU (2004). Directive 2004/107/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 15 December 2004 relating to arsenic, cadmium, mercury, nickel and polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons in ambient air. *OJ L 23*, 26.1.2005, p. 3–16.
- EU (2008). Directive 2008/50/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 21 May 2008 on ambient air quality and cleaner air for Europe. *OJ L 152*, 11.6.2008, pp. 1–44.
- EU (2011). Commission Implementing Decision No 2011/850/EU of 12 December 2011 laying down rules for Directives 2004/107/EC and 2008/50/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council as regards the reciprocal exchange of information and reporting on ambient air quality. *OJ L 335*, 17.12.2011, pp. 86–106.
- EU (2024). Directive (EU) 2024/2881 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 23 October 2024 on ambient air quality and cleaner air for Europe.
- WHO (2000). Air quality guidelines for Europe, *World Health Organization, Regional Office for Europe, Copenhagen*.
- WHO (2006). Air quality guidelines: Global update 2005 — Particulate matter, ozone, nitrogen dioxide and sulphur dioxide, *World Health Organization, Regional Office for Europe, Copenhagen*.
- WHO (2021). WHO global air quality guidelines. Particulate matter (PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀), ozone, nitrogen dioxide, sulfur dioxide and carbon monoxide. *World Health Organization, Geneva*.

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